

Study of Anxiety and Aggression Levels of Intercollegiate Volleyball Players For Better Performance

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Abstract:

The present study was conducted using the descriptive survey method. A total of 40 intercollegiate Volleyball players (20 boys and 20 girls) aged 18 to 25 years from Anantrao Pawar College of Engineering and Research, Parvati, Pune, were selected through purposive sampling. Two standardized psychological tools were used for data collection: the Sports Competitive State Anxiety Inventory developed by Rainer Martens, Vealey & Burton, and the Sports Aggression Inventory developed by Anand Kumar & Prem Shankar Shukla. After receiving permission from the college authorities, the players were briefed about the purpose of the research and were asked to complete the questionnaires. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The major findings revealed that both boys and girls exhibited high levels of competitive state anxiety and low levels of aggression.

Keywords: *Sports Competitive State Anxiety, Sports Aggression, Volleyball Players.*

Introduction:

Volleyball is a fast-paced team sport demanding quick reflexes, agility, hand-eye coordination, and the ability to adapt rapidly to changing situations. Besides technical and tactical proficiency, players are expected to maintain exceptional levels of mental concentration to perform effectively.

Psychological variables such as anxiety and aggression play a crucial role in determining athletic performance. Understanding these variables helps coaches, physical educationists, and trainers to design better training programmes and identify areas where players may require psychological intervention. This knowledge contributes to improved talent identification, mental preparation, and overall performance enhancement in both individual and team sports.

Objectives:

To examine the nature and distribution of psychological variables—specifically anxiety and aggression—among intercollegiate Volleyball boys and girls who have participated in collegiate-level tournaments.

Material and Method:

The study followed a descriptive survey research method. A purposive sample of 40 Volleyball players (20 boys and 20 girls) aged 18 to 25 years was selected from Anantrao Pawar College of Engineering and Research, Parvati, Pune.

Two standardized tools were used:

1. **Sports Competitive Anxiety Inventory** by Rainer Martens
 2. **Sports Aggression Inventory** by Anand Kumar and Prem Shankar Shukla
- Completed questionnaires were collected after ensuring that all items were

answered. Responses were scored according to the scoring keys provided by the authors of the tools. The collected data were then subjected to descriptive statistical analysis, including mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, variance, skewness, kurtosis) were used to analyze the data from both psychological variables.

Results:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Anxiety and Aggression among Volleyball Players

Category	Boys (Anxiety)	Girls (Anxiety)	Boys (Aggression)	Girls (Aggression)
N	20	20	20	20
Mean	60.32	63.08	13.02	12.17
Std. Error of Mean	0.75	0.64	0.29	0.27
Median	60.00	63.00	13.00	13.00
Mode	60.00	62.00	13.00	13.00
Std. Deviation	3.31	2.94	1.13	0.89
Variance	11.00	8.64	1.29	0.79
Skewness	0.127	0.360	-0.148	-0.145
Kurtosis	1.200	0.902	0.590	0.902

Interpretation:

- Boys' anxiety scores (Mean = 60.32) and girls' anxiety scores (Mean = 63.08) indicated **high levels of competitive anxiety**. The distribution patterns (skewness and kurtosis) suggest that both

groups displayed a near-normal distribution.

- Boys' aggression (Mean = 13.02) and girls' aggression (Mean = 12.17) were **low**, and the distribution of scores was also nearly normal.

Major Findings:

- Intercollegiate boys' Volleyball players exhibited **high competitive state anxiety** and **low aggression levels**.
- Intercollegiate girls' Volleyball players also showed **high competitive state anxiety** and **low aggression levels**.

The results support earlier findings by Jaskaran Singh Sindhu, Karanjit Singh, and Charanjit Singh (2011), who reported that female athletes tend to have higher anxiety levels, while male athletes typically display higher aggression. In the present study, both genders demonstrated uniform patterns of high anxiety and low aggression, suggesting sport-specific demands or psychological training influences.

Discussion:

The findings indicate that both male and female Volleyball players show increased levels of competitive anxiety but lower levels of aggression. High anxiety may influence performance during competitive situations; however, controlled levels can sometimes enhance alertness and readiness.

Conclusion:

This study provides valuable insights into the psychological characteristics of Volleyball players. The presence of high anxiety and low aggression suggests the need for psychological training to enhance coping mechanisms and competitive performance.

1. Anxiety and aggression significantly influence performance in sports and games.
2. Both variables can enhance or hinder performance depending on how they are managed.

Recommendations:

1. Similar studies can be conducted across different sports disciplines.
2. Future research may be carried out separately for school, college, and university-level Volleyball players.
3. Studies can be extended to inter-university, national, and international athletes.
4. A larger sample size is recommended for more reliable and generalizable results.
5. Coaches and selectors should consider athletes' mental health while evaluating performance and designing training programmes.

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